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DETERMINATION OF THE PERIOD OF CONTINUATION OF THE SUSPENSION FILTRATION PROCESS

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Annotation: When designing and setting up filters, it is impossible to do without reliable methods for calculating separation processes (filtering the suspension, washing and drying the sediment). Due to the lack of reliable engineering methods for calculating suspension separation processes, empirical methods are used predominantly when selecting and setting up filtration equipment. Calculations made on the basis of mathematical models of filtration, washing and drying are extremely rare and are of an exclusively estimated nature. Such experiments require specialized laboratory equipment; entail significant material and time costs; represent inconvenience to the customer, who is forced to send representative samples of his suspension up to 100-200 kg dry to the supplier company. The only way to solve all these issues is to compile a mathematical model of the suspension separation processes.

Keywords: suspension, filter, separation, residue, washing, calculation, process, concentrate, vacuum filters

ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЕ ПЕРИОДА ПРОДОЛЖЕНИЯ ПРОЦЕССА ФИЛЬТРАЦИИ СУСПЕНЗИИ

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Аннотация: При проектировании и настройке фильтров невозможно обойтись без надежных методов расчета процессов разделения (фильтрация суспензии, промывка и сушка осадка). Из-за отсутствия надежных инженерных методов расчета процессов разделения суспензий при выборе и наладке фильтрационного оборудования применяют преимущественно эмпирические методы. Расчеты, произведенные на основе математических моделей фильтрации, промывки и сушки, встречаются крайне редко и носят исключительно оценочный характер. Такие эксперименты требуют специального лабораторного оборудования; влекут за собой значительные материальные и временные затраты; представляют неудобства заказчику, который вынужден отправлять представительские образцы своей суспензии массой до 100-200 кг в сухом виде в компанию-поставщика. Единственный способ решить все эти вопросы – составить математическую модель процессов разделения суспензии.

Ключевые слова: суспензия, фильтр, сепарация, остаток, промывка, расчет, процесс, концентрат, вакуумные фильтры

Introduction. After conducting an in-depth analysis of the literature data on the processes of filtering the suspension, washing and drying the resulting sediment, a generalized mathematical description of the processes of separation of technological pulps on filter presses was compiled, taking

into account the hydrodynamic and heat exchange patterns of their occurrence. Based on the results of the work, averaged filterability characteristics of various suspensions on automated filter presses were obtained (Table 1).

Table 1 – Optimal performance of filtered suspensions

Concentrate	Size, microns	Moisture content, % by weight		Productivity, $\text{kg/m}^2\text{h}$	Purge air flow, l/min	Cycle duration, min
		initial	residual			
Cu	95% -50	35-40	6,61	400	350-400	11,5
Ni	82% -44+0	35-40	5,65	245	450-500	10,5
Cu-Ni	90% -63	30-40	8,05	373	180-260	10,5
Zn	90% -50	30-40	6,51	421	200-300	10,5
FeS2	70% -44+0	30-32	4,51	256	100-200	14,5

Calculation of the filtrate productivity or the duration of filtration with the formation of sediment can be carried out using the equation.

$$V^2 + 2VC = K\tau \quad (1)$$

where V is the volume of filtrate collected over time τ per unit surface; C is the volume of filtrate, which forms a sediment when passing through a unit of filter surface, with a resistance equal to the resistance of the filter partition; K is a constant that takes into account the physical and chemical properties of the material.

The material balance equation for the case under consideration will take the form:

$$\partial/\partial\tau(\sigma + \varepsilon c) + \omega_{\phi} \partial c / \partial h - D \partial^2 c / \partial h^2 = 0 \quad (2)$$

where σ is the retention of the solid phase, i.e. fraction of the layer volume occupied by settled particles; c is the volume concentration of the solid phase in the suspension; ω_{ϕ} – fictitious (calculated for the empty cross-section of the apparatus) flow velocity; D – diffusion coefficient. To calculate the speed of advance of the delay front, use the following relationship:

$$v_f = \omega_{\phi} c / \sigma. \quad (3)$$

Washing of sediments is the process of separating dissolved substances from the moisture of sediments and pulps by replacing the mother liquor with a washing solution, in particular with clean water, and serves as a means of increasing the extraction of valuable metals into solutions from the solid phase or increasing the purity of the solid product.

In order to increase the efficiency of this stage, washing on automated filter presses is carried out according to a direct-flow scheme, i.e.

Each subsequent filter chamber receives the washing solution from the previous one. In general, the process of washing the solid phase on filters can be considered by analogy with the filtration process, provided that the thickness of the sediment on the filter remains unchanged [2]. The washing rate is described by the equation

$$dV/d\tau = K/2(V_f + C)\mu_{pr}/\mu_f \tag{4}$$

where μ_f – viscosity of the filtrate;

μ_{pr} – viscosity of the washing liquid. The washing time on a periodic filter is calculated by the formula.

$$\tau_{np} = V_{np}(\alpha_f V_f + R_{fp})\mu_{pr}/p, \tag{5}$$

Here V_{pr} , V_f are the volumes of washing liquid and filtrate;

p – filtration pressure $R_{f.p.}$ – resistance of the filter partition;

$\alpha_f = R_{os}/V_{\text{umümi}}$ – average resistivity (by filtrate) (R_{oc} – total resistance of sediment;

$V_{\text{umümi}}$ – total volume of filtrate).

To calculate the washing of sediments using a sequential scheme, the formula is used

$$C_n = C_0(1/1 + V_{pr}/V), \tag{6}$$

where C_0 and C_n are the concentrations of the substance to be washed in the original and washed products;

V_{pr} and V – volumes of washing solution added for washing and retained by the solid phase;

n – number of washing stages.

To assess the efficiency of washing, the value E is used, equal to the ratio of the amount of the washed target component to its total amount in the liquid before washing [1-3]:

$$E = 1(1 - E_1)^m, \tag{7}$$

where m is the washing module, equal to the amount of washing liquid divided by the amount of liquid in the solid porous phase;

E_1 – flushing efficiency with a flushing module value equal to 1.

The theory of air drying of sediments uses a method for analyzing external heat and mass transfer, based on a joint consideration of the equations of motion and continuity of a viscous incompressible flow [1-5].

For the forced movement of air relative to the surface of the beach material, the following criterion heat transfer equation was obtained:

$$\text{Nu} = 2A\text{Re}^n \text{Pr}^{0.33} \text{Gu}^m, \quad (8)$$

Here $\text{Nu} = \alpha d / \lambda$ – Nusselt criterion;

$\text{Pr} = \nu / a$ – Prandtl criterion;

$\text{Gu} = (T - T_m) / T$ – parametric criterion;

T – air temperature;

T_m – wet thermometer temperature;

α – heat transfer coefficient;

λ – thermal conductivity coefficient of the drying agent;

d – 6 characteristic geometric size of the body;

ν – kinematic coefficient of liquid viscosity; a is the thermal diffusivity coefficient. The equation for the Nusselt mass transfer criterion has the form:

$$\text{Nu}_m = 2 + A' \text{Re}^{n'} \text{Re}^{0.33} \text{Gu}^{m'}. \quad (9)$$

For the intensity of water evaporation from the surface of a stationary layer of spherical particles into a drying agent filtering through the layer, the following equation was obtained:

$$\text{Nu}_m = 0.9 \text{Re}^{0.5} \text{Pr}^{0.33}, \quad \text{Re} = (7.55 - 8.7) \cdot 10^4, \quad (10)$$

where the determining size is the diameter of the spheres, and the air speed is related to the full cross-section of the apparatus. The values of the parameters of equations (9) and (10) depending on the range of changes in the Reynolds criterion are given in Table. 2:

Table 2 – Coefficients of criterion equations for drying dispersed materials

Re	A	n	m	A'	n'	m'
1.2·10 ²	1.07	0.48	0.175	0.83	0.53	0.135
3.15·10 ³ – 2.2·10 ⁴	0.51	0.61	0.175	0.49	0.61	0.135
2.2·10 ⁴ – 3.15·10 ⁵	0.027	0.90	0.175	0.025	0.90	0.135

Experimental part. In order to test this model, determine the type and filtering constants, a series of experiments were carried out. The studies were carried out using nylon filter fabric article number 56027 at a pressure drop

of 500 mm Hg. The measured values were the volume of the formed filtrate and the time required for its formation.

The experiment was repeated several times at different temperatures (60°C and 90°C) and different filtration durations. The collected experimental data were subsequently used to calculate the regression coefficients C and K corresponding to the system of equations (4) (Table 3, Fig. 1). To find them, the least squares method was used. The duration of filtration to obtain a given volume of filtrate with known filtration constants was calculated using the equation.

Table 3 – Summary table of quantities included in the filtering equation

Quantity	Designation	Dimensions	Numerical value at	
			60 °C	90 °C
Filtration surface	F	м 2	3,85·10 ⁻³	3,85·10 ⁻³
Pressure difference	Δp	Па	6,67·10 ⁴	6,67·10 ⁴
Dynamic viscosity coefficient of the liquid phase of the suspension	$\mu_{ж}$	Па·с	1,027·10 ⁻³	0,668·10 ⁻³
Ratio of sediment and filtrate volumes	a_0	м 3 /м ³	9,625·10 ⁻²	9,206·10 ⁻²
Resistance of the filter baffle.	$R_{\phi,II}$	1/м	0,0	5,464·10 ¹⁰
Specific volumetric resistance of sediment	$r_{об.}$	1/м ²	9,966·10 ¹³	1,522·10 ¹⁴

Creating a generalized mathematical model of the processes of filtering a suspension, washing and drying the resulting sediment is a solution to a major practical problem. It allows you to predict with high probability the filterability of a particular suspension on a filter press, without resorting to direct experiment; in the shortest possible time and at low cost, adjust the filter to the required performance and residual humidity. The indicators of suspension filtration obtained in the experimental part, although not final, still give grounds to assert that temperature has a significant influence on the process, and, therefore, the need to take into account heat exchange in the layer of dispersed particles during filtration, which is reflected in the theoretical part of this work, can be considered justified. The direction of further research is to refine the generalized mathematical model, supplement it with the necessary experimental data and compile a computer program that

implements the algorithm proposed above for calculating suspension separation processes [5-8].

Figure 1 – Algorithm for calculating continuous filters

Conclusion.

The parameters contained in the parallelogram are determined experimentally. Parameters enclosed in rectangular frames are calculated using standard or proposed formulas.

The influence of the main factors of the treated suspension on the parameters of the processes of filtration and dewatering of sediments – the particle size of the solid phase and the porosity of the resulting sediment – has been established.

An empirical equation is proposed for determining the coefficient A' in the Kozeny-Karlan equation depending on the average diameter of the particles of the solid phase of the separated suspensions. An empirical equation has been obtained for the kinetics of the dehydration process of sediments of separated concentrates.

A dependence was obtained to determine the air flow rate on vacuum filters. The proposed methods for selecting the most efficient components of equipment can be used when designing filter departments

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